

Effectiveness of Poverty Management Based on Economic Independence Locals in Gorontalo Province

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Abstract:- This type of research is qualitative through a phenomenological approach, while the results show that the problem of poverty is a classic problem that until now has not been able to be overcome optimally, various programs implemented have not been able to reduce poverty rates and the tendency that the number of poor people increases over time, so policies based on improving people's welfare are needed through the motivation of self-reliance supported by self-employment. by the aspects of money, training and guidance on an ongoing basis, in addition to government synergy between all stake holders and the business world, the world of education needs to be built to jointly prosper society macro and micro.

Keywords:- Poverty, Strategy, Policy, Development, Economy.

I. INTRODUCTION

Poverty phenomenon that occurs in almost all cities and districts in Indonesia, and conditions become homework for regional heads where poverty is not a new problem, meaning that since the State of Indonesia became independent then poverty has existed and poverty development is difficult to eliminate, many poverty alleviation programs until 2022 are made, but poverty remains as if it has never been extinguished (dead).

The gorontalo provincial government is the 32nd province in Indonesia, also not separated from the problem of poverty, various poverty alleviation programs made are only able to reduce no more than 1 percent of the total poverty and even though the nature is up and down, there is a decline to be grateful, for the long term a synergistic strategy is needed to reduce the poverty rate.

The cause of the high poverty rate in Gorontalo is the low productivity and added value of the agricultural sector which is the main livelihood of the population. "There are four districts that are below the average PDRB per capita district / city, namely Bone Bolango Regency, North Gorontalo Regency, Boalemo Regency, and Gorontalo Regency. This inequality is due to the condition of uneven geographical distribution of income," gorontalo community development index (HDI) is still low because of the low achievement in three main components, namely education, health, and community income level. Gorontalo's poverty rate of 15.83 percent is still high, above the national average. However, in 2014-2018 the figure continued to

decrease faster than the national. The poverty rate of all districts in Gorontalo is still above the national average, except in Gorontalo City. HdI in Gorontalo Province of 70.81 in 2017 is still lagging behind the national.

II. PROBLEM FORMULATION

- How is the poverty condition in Gorontalo Province
- How to overcome poverty based on local economic independence in Gorontalo Province

III. THEORETICAL BASIS

A. Definition of Poverty

Poverty is a condition of inability in terms of primary needs so that this condition is related to life. Poverty is identified with powerlessness in potential sectors, poverty does not stand alone, poverty is not always identified with the absence of work, lack of nutrition, inadequate housing, but poverty also includes a mindset and perspective related to the economy.

In America some psychologists are aware of some of the disadvantages of low incomes that go with America. Yet the search for a clear process of the impact of poverty on children has focused almost exclusively on psychosocial characteristics in families, particularly negative parents (Bornstein & Bradley, 2003; G. H. Brody et al., 1994; Conger & Elder, 1994; Luthar, 1999; Mcloyd, 1998 in Gary W. Evans, 2004). The focus on psychosocial processes is limited in two respects. First, psychological research on poverty has neglected the physical settings that low-income children and families inhabit. Families live in both the social and physical worlds (Bradley, 1999; Evans, Kliever, & Martin, 1991; Parke, 1978; Wachs, 2000; Wohlwill & Heft, 1987 in Gary W. Evans, 2004), and each has an impact well-documented in human development. Second, poor children face a frightening array of suboptimal psychosocial and physical conditions.

B. Types of Poverty

To influence poverty outcomes and distributions of environmental shocks in J. Edward Taylor and Thomas Reardon (1996). Low inequality would mean that the poor bear a greater share of the negative impacts of the aggregate economic contraction. Low inequality will then be a mixed blessing for the poor; helping them share in the benefits of growth, but also exposing them to the costs of contraction in Martin Ravallion (1997).

Usman (2003: 33) says that poverty is a condition of deprivation of sources for meeting basic needs in the form of food, clothing, housing, education and health and their lives are in need. While the understanding of the problem of poverty, according to Sumodiningrat (1999: 45):

According to Suparlan (1995: 11) poverty can be defined as a low standard of living, namely the existence of a low standard of living, a level of material deficiency in a number or group of people compared to the standard of living generally applicable in the society concerned.

C. Public Policy Theory

Public policy is what the government chooses to do or not to do. Carl Friedrich in Dede Mariana (2010) explains that a policy is a series of actions or activities proposed by a person, group, or government in a certain environment where there are obstacles (difficulties) and possibilities (opportunities) in which the policy is proposed. to be useful in overcoming them to achieve the intended goal.

The public policy process, at least includes: 1) Problem formulation; 2) Forecasting; 3) Recommendations; 4) Monitoring; 5) Evaluation. Innovative public policies must always: 1) be based on the public interest; 2) Planning, implementation, and monitoring, as well as their evaluation involve public participation; 3) The formulation always moves dynamically in accordance with the development of public aspirations.

There are many public policy terminology, depending on which angle we interpret it from. Easton provides a definition of public policy as the authoritative allocation of values for the whole society or as a forced allocation of values to all members of society 2). Laswell and Kaplan also define public policy as a projected program of goals, values, and practice or a program of achieving goals, values in directed practices. Another definition of public policy is also expressed by Anderson who states public policy as a purposive course of action followed by an actor on set an actors in dealing with a problem or matter of concern or as an action that has a specific purpose followed and implemented by an actor or group of actors to solve a problem.

Aspects of public policy according to Dye (1995) in Susy Susilawati (2007) can be defined as everything the government does, why they do it, and the results that make a life together appear different (what government do, why they do it, and what difference it is). makes). Dumn (2003) in Susy Susilawati (2007) suggests that public policy is a complex pattern of interdependence of interdependent collective choices, including decisions not to act, made by government agencies or offices.

Stakeholders here are individuals, groups, or institutions who have an interest in a policy. Stakeholders of this policy can be actors involved in the formulation and implementation of policies, beneficiaries and victims who are harmed by a public policy. There are three stakeholder groups namely key stakeholders, primary, and secondary stakeholders (Suharto, 2007 in Yuli et al, 2012). While the public policy process itself consists of three main stages,

namely formulation, implementation, and evaluation (in Yuli et al, 2012).

IV. RESEARCH METHODS

Types of Qualitative Research Through Phenomenological Approach

V. DISCUSSION

A. POVERTY RATES IN GORONTALO PROVINCE

The poverty rate in Gorontalo Province is around 15.83 percent, based on a survey in September 2018. Compared to the percentage of poor people in March 2018 of 16.81 percent, it means that the poverty rate has decreased by 0.98 points.

During the period March 2018 - September 2018, the percentage of poor people in urban areas and rural areas decreased. In urban areas the percentage of the poor population fell from 5.26 percent in March 2018, to 4.45 percent in September 2018, which means a decrease of 0.81 points. While in rural areas there was a decrease of 0.23 points, from 24.09 percent in March 2018 to 23.86 percent in September 2018. According to the number count, the poor population in September 2018 was 188.30 thousand people, while the number of poor people in March 2018 was 198.51 thousand people.. Thus the number of poor people as many as 10.21 thousand people, of which 88.37 percent live in rural areas and the rest in urban areas. The cause of the high poverty rate in Gorontalo is the low productivity and added value of the agricultural sector which is the main livelihood of the population. "There are four districts that are below the average PDRB per capita district / city, namely Bone Bolango Regency, North Gorontalo Regency, Boalemo Regency, and Gorontalo Regency. This inequality is due to the condition of uneven geographical distribution of income," gorontalo community development index (HDI) is still low because of the low achievement in three main components, namely education, health, and community income level. Gorontalo's poverty rate of 15.83 percent is still high, above the national average. However, in 2014-2018 the figure continued to decrease faster than the nationally.

B. POVERTY MANAGEMENT STRATEGIES IN GORONTALO PROVINCE

There are three ways to minimize poverty.

- acceleration of economic growth in Gorontalo Province through improving the investment climate to facilitate capital formation, as well as increasing added value and strengthening the potential of the agricultural sector.
- comprehensive social protection, expanded access to basic services such as education and health to the poor, and increased productive economic capacity through market and financial access opening programs.
- provision of education and health infrastructure and improving the quality of human resources.

VI. STRATEGIC OF GOVERNMENT FOR OVERCOME POVERTY

A. Government Efforts

There are fundamental changes made by the provincial government, to reduce poverty rates. One of them is by ensuring that recipients of social assistance are on target and in accordance with what is needed. First the target of aid recipients, it turns out that so far there are those who should not be worthy of receiving but given assistance, "In addition, continued Rusli, his party continues to intensify data collection to villages to find anyone who deserves to receive program assistance.

The recipient's data must refer to the database of the National Team for the Acceleration of Poverty Reduction (TNP2K) or the citizens who really deserve it. According to the Gorontalo Provincial Government, the reduction in poverty rate was also influenced by various social programs implemented throughout 2018. One of them is the NKRI Peduli Social Service program. The program, which is rolled out in each sub-district once a week, contains cheap market operations and the distribution of compensation from Baznas worth Rp100,000 per person to 1,000 poor people. In addition to subsidizing prices. For example, rice is sold in the market for Rp10,000 in subsidies of Rp 3000 so that the rice is sold for Rp7,000. There are also spices, cooking oil, fish, eggs and others," the same thing was also expressed by the Head of the Regional Planning, Research and Development Agency (BAPPEDA) Budiyanto Sidiki. According to him, the successful market operation program reduced the money expenditure of the poor and suppressed inflation in the area. The social program is strengthened by central government programs such as Beras Sejahtera (Rastra), Non-Cash Food Assistance (BPNT) program and Family Hope Program (PKH) to 68,000 Beneficiary Families (KPM). There are also other programs financed through APBD such as BPNT-D for 35,000 KPM, fish boat assistance, corn seed assistance, rice and fertilizer, livestock, cooling boxed motorcycles for fish sellers, and fish assistance for school students. Economist from Hasanuddin University, Agus Salim, said the economy of Gorontalo Province is still dominated by government investment and most people work in the agricultural sector. He argued that Gorontalo must grow the processing industry if it wants to balance the region's economy. The industry is needed because it can provide added value to commodities produced by farmers. "The agricultural processing industry also has an effect that can be enjoyed by the whole community. In addition, the processing industry is also able to absorb more labor and is able to absorb a relatively more educated workforce," he said. He revealed his analysis related to anomalies that occurred, when economic growth tended to strengthen in 2017 but the open unemployment rate increased. He considered it indicates that Gorontalo labor productivity levels are still low, the labor market tends to absorb uneducated labor. Gorontalo province is so far still supported by the agricultural sector, while the sector does not need an educated workforce. As a result, most of the educated workforce in Gorontalo is not well absorbed. "What must be done by local governments is to maintain the growth of the agricultural, forestry and fisheries sectors and

encourage exports and development of the processing industry," he added. Agus explained that the absorption of government budgets through state budget funds and APBD must be maximized every year, because Gorontalo's economy is still very dependent on the budget. "The use of APBD must also be ensured its use for useful and targeted things to reduce poverty," he said.

VII. ANALYSIS OF LOCAL ECONOMIC INDEPENDENCE

Looking at the strategy of handling poverty in Gorontalo Province according to researchers has not touched the root of the problem, the concept of poverty management made by the government is still short-term such as price subsidy assistance, rice assistance for the poor, cash assistance made by the central government that is passed on throughout the provinces and regencies in Indonesia is only short-term., The effect when the assistance provided does not run then the community will return poor, the existence of food assistance and money given to the community this will make the community not creative and tend to always hope, the effect from day to day the ability of the community will decrease, both in terms of motivation, initiative, creativity and finally will appear lazy nature so as to produce a society that has low human resources., People if they want to get out of poverty then it needs to be cultivated entrepreneurial spirit, the community needs to be encouraged to be able to make productive business efforts so that they are able to meet the needs of life both primary, secondary and tertier, then the government must make development policies both in the form of business capital assistance, training, guidance and assistance in terms of marketing people's business results that can water or encourage people to be creative in economic activities, For this reason, the government must invite entrepreneurs and the world of education to jointly build the economy so that the community is more prosperous.

VIII. CONCLUSION

Poverty is a social phenomenon and is a classic problem that until now has not been able to be overcome optimally, various programs made have not been able to reduce poverty rates that continue to grow and the tendency that the number of poor people increases, for that policies based on improving people's welfare through the motivation of entrepreneurial independence supported by the money aspect, Training and guidance in a sustainable manner, in addition to government synergy between all stake holders and the business world, the world of education needs to be built to jointly prosper the community macro and micro

REFERENCES

- [1.] Asep Sudrajat (2013), "Unemployment and Poverty in Indonesia", <http://jajukal.blogspot.com/>.
- [2.] Alwi (2006). "Concept of Good Governance in the Concept of Regional Autonomy", *Journal of Administrative and Policy Analysis*, Volume 3, Number 1, January – April 2006.
- [3.] Burhanuddin (2009), "Public Service Policy for Education in West Sumbawa Regency of west southeast Nusa Province", FKIP Mataram University 2009.
- [4.] Bambang and Muntiani (2012). "Field Work Practice Management Information System in Web-Based Information Systems Study Program", *Seruni FTI UNSA 2012 Volume 1* ISSN: 2302-1136.
- [5.] Dede Mariana (2010), "Regional Autonomy and Policy Innovation", *governance*, Vol. 1, No. 1, November 2010.
- [6.] Dedi Rudyanto (2012), "The Influence of The Council's Knowledge on Fencing on Regional Financial Supervision (APBD), with Community Participation and Public Policy Transparency as Moderating Variables (Empirical Studies in the Karanganyar Regency DPRD)", *Publication Journal of the Faculty of Economics, University of Muhammadiyah Surakarta* 2012.
- [7.] Gary W. Evans (2004), "The Environment of Childhood Poverty", *American Psychologist* Vol. 59, No. 2, 77–92.
- [8.] Hadi Sasana (2011), "Analysis of Regional Spending Determinants in West Java Province Regencies/Cities in the Era of Fiscal Autonomy and Decentralization", *Journal of Business and Economics (JBE)*, March 2011, Vol. 18, No. 1, ISSN: 1412-3126.
- [9.] Idawati Pandia (2008), "Public Opinion On the Role of Local Print Media in the Development of Horticultural Agriculture (Survey in Ndokum Siroga Village and Surbakti Village, Simpang District Four Karo Regencies)", *BBPPKI Medan*, 2008.
- [10.] Julisar An-Naf (2005), "Sustainable Development and Its Relevance to Indonesia", *Madani Journal: Issue II*, November 2005.
- [11.] J. Edward Taylor and Thomas Reardon (1996), "Agroclimatic Shock, Income Inequality, and Poverty: Evidence from Burkina Faso" *World Development*, Vol. 24, No. 5.
- [12.] Mochamad, et al (2012). "Development of Computer Engineering Learning Media Network Class X Odd Semester at Vocational High School Of Taruna Bangsa Pati Based on Interactive Multimedia", *Indonesian Journal on Computer Science Speed (IJCSS) 13 FTI UNSA Vol 9 No 3 – December 2012 - ejournal.unsa.ac.id*.
- [13.] Martin Ravallion (1995). "Growth and poverty: Evidence for developing countries in the 1980s", *Economics Letters* 48 (1995) 411-417.
- [14.] Martin Ravallion (1997), "Can high-inequality developing countries escape absolute poverty?", *Economics Letters*, Vol. 56 (1997): 51-57
- [15.] Paul Mosley and David Hulme (2009) "Microenterprise Finance. Is there a conflict between growth and poverty alleviation?", ISBN 0-203-88276-8 Master e-book ISBN.
- [16.] Purbayudan Retno (2005). "Analysis of Regional Native Income (PAD) and Factors Affecting It in Efforts to Implement Regional Autonomy in Kediri Regency", *Journal of Development Dynamics*, Vol. 2 No. 1 / lull 2005: 9 – 18.
- [17.] RM Riadi and Caska (2008), "Growth and Inequality of Interregional Economic Development in Riau Province", *Journal of Industry and Urban* Volume XII Number 21, February 2008.
- [18.] Redatin, et al (2012), "The Impact of Village Competition Implementation on Community Empowerment in Development in West Kalimantan (Study in Pal IX Village, Kakap River District, Kubu Raya Regency)", *PMIS-UNTAN-PSS Thesis Journal*-2013.
- [19.] Rofiuddin Mohammad (2012), "Analysis of Regional Financial Performance in Madura Island, East Java Province in the Era of Regional Autonomy in 2005-2009", *Publication Journal of the Faculty of Economics, University of Muhammadiyah Surakarta* 2012.
- [20.] Susy, (2007). "Public Policy Analysis in the Field of Occupational Safety and Health in Tasikmalaya City", Thesis, Diponegoro University Semarang 2007.
- [21.] Yuli et al (2012), "Participatory and Communicative Public Policy", *Journal of Public Policy*, Volume 3, Number 2, October 2012, pp. 59-141.